

The Guaranteed Detection of the Seismoacoustic Emission Source in the C-OTDR Systems

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Abstract : A method is proposed for stable detection of seismoacoustic sources in C-OTDR systems that guarantee given upper bounds for probabilities of type I and type II errors. Properties of the proposed method are rigorously proved. The results of practical applications of the proposed method in a real C-OTDR-system are presented in this.

Keywords : guaranteed detection, C-OTDR systems, change point, interval estimation

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